

Organic Non-Toxic Rechargeable Batteries in Food Packaging: a Feasibility Study

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Abstract— Traditional energy sources, such as alkaline batteries, cannot be in direct contact with food due to health hazards. However, a recently developed battery, constituted only by food-grade materials, overcomes this limitation as it can be used in direct contact with food without any contamination risk.

In this work, we assess the feasibility of adopting an edible battery to power up traditional electronics for sensors-on-food or sensors-in-package applications. The feasibility study is divided into three main analyses. First, the lifetime of the battery against multiple charge-discharge cycles is assessed. In our experiments, the battery maintains a capacity of $\sim 6 \mu\text{Ah}$ after 100 cycles. Then, the study progressed to resistive sensors. As a test case, we demonstrated that data obtained from thermistors and photoresistors powered up by the battery have a cross-correlation coefficient > 0.99 with respect to using a traditional power supply as the energy source. Finally, the edible battery is successfully used to power OPAMP-based circuits performing amplification and filtering. This study indicates that, although more research is necessary to enhance the battery's performance, edible batteries represent a feasible alternative for supplying power for a limited time to basic low-power circuits.

Index Terms — Non-toxic battery, edible battery, edible electronics, biodegradable electronics, green electronics, agrifood sensors.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the last decades, the agricultural food production chain, also known as agrifood, has experienced a digital revolution that has deeply transformed every stage of the process, including production, transport, storage, and consumption [1, 2]. The pervasive use of sensors in networks to evaluate food storage conditions together with artificial intelligence is one of the key characteristics of the digital revolution [3 – 6]. Thus, a growing number of sensors integrated into smart food packaging have enabled strategies to increase food quality and safety while reducing food waste [7]. A wide range of sensors for food monitoring have been documented [3, 5, 8 - 15] and visual indicators for temperature, pH, and gases, are widely employed nowadays [8]. Although these indicators benefit from not requiring an energy source and being low-cost and user-friendly, they are limited by providing only qualitative information. Quantitative measurements and digitalization of the information are instead possible using active sensors. External labels implemented using commercial components and powered by coin cell batteries have been demonstrated for

monitoring environmental parameters [5], including temperature [9], humidity [10], and light [3] among others. However, the integration of active sensors inside the food package remains very limited because of safety concerns of direct contact between food and the sensing node. In particular, the use of traditional batteries (e.g. alkaline, Li metal, Li-ion) in direct contact with food is not viable because hazardous compounds could migrate and contaminate food. Traditional batteries contain toxic and corrosive materials, including heavy metals and metal oxides as electrodes, and caustic and organic solvents as electrolytes [16, 17]. The caustic salt KOH contained in the electrolyte of alkaline batteries might cause respiratory and skin irritation, while organic compounds and salts used in Li batteries can release hazardous chemicals like HF, HCN, COS, Li compounds, and ionic liquids [17]. Heavy metals, like Co and Ni used in the electrodes, can also contaminate food and then be ingested, leading to genetic damage [17, 18]. Additionally, deploying traditional batteries for large-scale and disposable applications, such as sensors-on-food or sensors-in-package, would have a dramatic environmental impact due to electronic-waste accumulation issues, therefore it is not advisable. Battery-less solutions, such as NFC-powered devices, have been proposed as a viable alternative [11 - 14], measuring temperature [12], air pressure [12, 13], storage time [12], pH level [14], and CO₂ concentration [14]. Although they avoid the use of traditional batteries, thus increasing the safety of the system, they suffer from not being fully energy-autonomous.

Adopting safer energy sources instead of traditional ones is considered a promising alternative to deliver energy autonomous sensing nodes. For instance, triboelectric nanogenerators have been used to create a self-powered ammonia sensor [13]; a temperature-activated galvanic cell has also been demonstrated for sensor-on-food applications to track the cold chain of the product [15]. Recently, an organic non-toxic rechargeable battery was developed using only food-based materials [19]. The battery was implemented in the context of edible electronics, an emerging research field exploring the electronic properties of food-derived materials to produce non-toxic electronic circuits [20]. Since all the materials involved in the fabrication of the battery are food-grade, the battery is inherently safe-to-eat and can be disposed of as food waste at the end of its lifetime.

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Fig. 1. (a) The edible battery developed in [19] has a size comparable to traditional AA batteries. (b) Future application scenario of the edible battery. The battery is inherently safe upon ingestion therefore it can support applications in direct contact with food, including sensing applications inside the food package.

In this work, we experimentally assess the feasibility of adopting edible batteries to power up traditional electronics sensors producing hybrid systems. To this aim, we explore the use of the recently developed rechargeable battery [19] that was selected as one of the best innovations of 2023 by the TIME [21] and preliminary assessed in [22]. We first quantify the stability of the battery upon multiple charge-discharge cycles using different current levels. Then, we interconnect the battery with simple commercial temperature and light sensors, to assess the likelihood of the output with respect to using a traditional power supply. Testing progressed to active circuits using a low-power operational amplifier (OPAMP), which is suitable for multiple readout circuits including amplification and filtering. Our findings demonstrate that, although the current version of the battery has certain limitations, the use of edible batteries instead of traditional ones is indeed feasible, especially in the case of food-contact disposable and low-power applications.

II. EDIBLE ELECTRONICS FOR FOOD MONITORING

A. The battery

Edible electronics originated from ingestible electronics [23], with the aim of delivering safer technologies for gastrointestinal (GI) tract monitoring. However, in a short time, the scientific community realized that this technology holds wider potential in alternative application scenarios because of its peculiar advantages. Current edible electronics components can find applications not only for in-body applications [24] but also for out-of-body scenarios [25, 26]. Nonetheless, the development of edible power sources is a prerequisite for delivering any edible circuit, regardless of the final application. Recent years have already seen the development of edible supercapacitors, which store energy by taking advantage of the creation of an electrical double layer [27 - 30], but they are more suited for delivering power bursts rather than constant output. Edible fuel cells, which use fuel to produce energy, have also been

demonstrated, such as an ethanol-based fuel cell [31]. However, fuel cells typically exhibit a limited volumetric energy density. An edible rechargeable battery, made entirely from food-grade materials, which employs two redox-active molecules, riboflavin, and quercetin, as the anodic and cathodic materials respectively, was recently demonstrated (Fig. 1a) [19]. Riboflavin, commonly known as vitamin B₂, is found in many different foods like almonds, egg white, and meat, and is sold also in the form of vitamin supplements and food colouring agents (E 101). Quercetin is a flavonol found in different vegetables and leaves, like capers, coriander, and kale. Activated carbon (AC), was used to prepare composites with the small molecules to create a conductive path for electrons flowing to and from the redox centres. AC is a food additive approved in the European Union as E 153 and produced from carbon-rich sources like bamboo, coconut husk, and wood. AC is used as a dye but also as a dietary supplement in capsules [32]. The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) does not express concerns about the maximum daily intake of hundreds of mg/kg reported in the food industry [33]. Active-redox inks were prepared by mixing the AC-small molecules composites with ethyl cellulose (E 462), used as a binder, and dissolved in ethanol. The inks were then drop cast on conductive edible electrodes, made by laminating edible gold leaves (E 175) onto ethyl cellulose films. The battery was assembled by placing the anode and the cathode in a stacked configuration, using nori algae, previously soaked in the electrolyte (1 M water solution of NaHSO₄, E 514ii), as a separator. Finally, the device was encapsulated in beeswax, a natural wax produced by honeybees and EU-approved (E 901) for use as glazing agent and surface protection. In humans, toxicological tests provide a “No Observed Adverse Effect Level” (NOAEL) up to 1.1 g/kg [34]. Beeswax also has interesting antibacterial properties [35], which makes it an ideal candidate for food contact applications. The inherent safety of the edible battery could be exploited in a wide range of application scenarios.

Fig. 2 (a) Battery galvanostatic charging-discharging curves (100 cycles) at $100 \mu\text{A}$ between 0.6 and 0.8 V, showing (b) battery charging and (c) battery discharging time/capacity in these conditions. (d) Battery galvanostatic charging-discharging curves (19 cycles) between 0.6 and 0.8 V (charging at $200 \mu\text{A}$ and discharging at $50 \mu\text{A}$). (e) Battery charging time at $200 \mu\text{A}$ from 0.6 to 0.8 V for 19 cycles. (f) Battery discharging time at $50 \mu\text{A}$ from 0.8 to 0.6 V for 19 cycles and corresponding capacity.

B. Application scenarios

In agrifood, non-toxic batteries, such as the one developed in [19], might find application as energy source for sensing nodes inside the food package in direct contact with food (Fig 1b). Future sensing nodes could include several functionalities, such as sensing, signal conditioning, and data transmission, aiming at identifying specific products that are no longer suitable for human consumption (e.g. due to a disruption of the storage chain). At the end of their lifetime, the battery can be composted as food waste or reused/recycled when possible. So far, a large variety of edible sensors have been implemented [15, 20-26, 36-43]. Therefore, in the future we envision the implementation of fully edible sensing nodes, thus removing the residual contamination risk associated with the use of other traditional components. Edible technology will enable the development of novel systems with wide application in healthcare for gastrointestinal tract monitoring as well as digital agriculture. This feasibility study aims to demonstrate that using an edible battery, instead of traditional power supply methods in a sensing node, maintains a satisfactory quality of the collected data. The feasibility analysis is composed of three studies: (i) battery lifetime; (ii) compatibility with resistive sensors; (iii) compatibility with active components. As a case study, we focus our efforts on discussing sensing (temperature and light) and signal conditioning scenarios (OPAMP circuits). Since this represents a first-of-a-kind study on edible components, we focus on simple circuit implementations using resistive sensors and established signal conditioning active circuits.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Battery lifetime

The edible batteries, fabricated as in [19] with an active area of 1 cm^2 , can deliver $100 \mu\text{A}$ for five minutes, with an operating voltage of 0.65 V. To test the durability of the battery, we performed 100 galvanostatic charging-discharging measurements at $100 \mu\text{A}$ between 0.6 and 0.8 V, using a MultiPalmSens4 potentiostat which provides a standard platform for battery testing, as in [19]. The first cycle of the test (from 0 to 0.8 V) was excluded. Data indicates that after 100 charging-discharging cycles, the battery is still operational (Fig. 2a). During the cyclic test, both the charging time (Fig. 2b) and the discharging time (Fig. 2c) suffer a decrease, which indicates a reduction in the performance of the battery. However, after 100 cycles we estimate that the battery can still provide a current of $100 \mu\text{A}$ for $\sim 214 \text{ s}$ with a resulting capacity of $\sim 6 \mu\text{Ah}$. The charging time can be reduced by increasing the charging current. Fig. 2d shows 19 charging-discharging cycles using a charging current of $200 \mu\text{A}$ and a discharge current of $50 \mu\text{A}$. In this condition and after 19 cycles, the charging time is $\sim 155 \text{ s}$ and the discharging time is $\sim 550 \text{ s}$ yielding a capacity of $\sim 7.6 \mu\text{Ah}$.

B. Resistive Sensors

The feasibility study focused on simple resistive sensors, i.e. temperature (thermistors) and light (photoresistors) sensors. To test the edible battery with a thermistor, a voltage divider circuit was implemented using a discrete pull-up resistor ($100 \text{ k}\Omega \pm 5\%$ by RS Pro) and a commercial negative temperature coefficient thermistor (MF52B $100 \text{ k}\Omega$ at 25°C).

Fig. 3. (a) Schematic of the circuits tested for resistive sensing. The two test circuits are identical apart from the power source which is respectively a power supply (reference) and an edible battery. (b) Comparison between the output obtained when using the edible battery vs power supply for temperature sensing for three different experiments. (c) Signal deviations during a cooling cycle from 50 to 30°C. (d) Comparison between the output obtained when using the edible battery vs power supply (reference) for light intensity sensing for three different experiments. (e) A typical response from the two circuits using an intermittent light at 1 Hz. (f) The probability density function of the error for the entire dataset.

The voltage divider was connected to an edible battery using standard wiring. An identical voltage divider was also implemented, and 0.7 V was supplied with a power supply (Agilent E3647A). The output of both the voltage dividers was measured using a 2-channel precision source meter (Keysight B2912A). Fig. 3a shows a schematic of the two circuits under test. Both circuits were exposed to identical controlled temperature changes using an environmental chamber (Memmert HPP110ecoplus). As shown in Fig. 3b, several datasets from the temperature sensor powered by the edible battery and the power supply have a high degree of similarity: the average cross-correlation coefficient between the two conditions was 0.99 ± 0.01 . The observed small deviations seem to increase over time and are probably due to the progressive discharge of the battery (Fig. 3c).

To test the edible battery with a light intensity sensor, a similar voltage divider circuit was implemented using a pull-up resistor ($56 \text{ k}\Omega \pm 5\%$ by RS Pro) and a commercial photoresistor (GL5516) whose resistance is inversely dependent on the intensity of incident light. While this circuit was powered by the edible battery, an identical voltage divider was also implemented and powered up with 0.7 V from the same power supply (see Fig. 3a). Both circuits were first exposed to dark conditions. The light intensity was then progressively increased using a white LED (Thorlabs MCWHL2-C4) controlled in current using a driver (Thorlabs DC2200) until the saturation of the sensor.

The datasets in Fig. 3d illustrate that the curves acquired using the edible battery as a power source are virtually identical to the ones collected using the power supply, with an even higher

average cross-correlation coefficient of 0.998 ± 0.001 . Elevated likelihood was also observed when illuminating the sensor with intermittent light (strobe frequency 1 Hz, see Fig. 3e).

All the datasets acquired with resistive sensors were used to extract the probability density function of the measurement error. The error (e) was calculated as:

$$e = \text{Reference} \frac{\Delta V}{V_0} (\%) - \text{Battery} \frac{\Delta V}{V_0} (\%)$$

producing a dataset just below 100k datapoints. The resulting probability density (shown in Fig. 3f) also includes fluctuations due to sensor-to-sensor, measurement-to-measurement, environmental, and instrumental noise, and therefore it is not exclusively dependent on the use of the edible battery. The extracted probability density function was fitted with a skewed normal distribution model yielding a mean value of 4.1% and a standard deviation of 3.5%. The skew observed in the distribution of the error is probably associated with the discharging effect of the battery over time, which is particularly perceivable in longer measurements resulting in a lower effective voltage when compared to the stable output of a power supply.

C. Active Circuits

Most of the OPAMP currently on the market operate at a supply voltage higher than 1 V, which is incompatible with the use of a single edible battery. Extensive efforts are underway to further minimize the power requirements of opamps [44, 45], and only a small number of commercial components can operate at lower voltages.

Fig. 4. (a) Test setup of the edible battery for an inverting amplifying circuit (gain ~ 2.5 V/V). (b) Amplified output (red) when using a 50 Hz sine wave input with a peak-to-peak voltage of 10 mV (blue). (c) Amplified output (red) when using a 100 Hz sine wave input with a peak-to-peak voltage of 10 mV (blue). (d) Amplified output (red) when using a 130 Hz sine wave input with a peak-to-peak voltage of 10 mV (blue). (e) Test setup of the edible battery for the buffer-RC cascade. (f) Bode diagram (amplitude) of the implemented low-pass filter (cutoff frequency ~ 59.13 kHz). (g) Output (red) when using a 1 kHz sine wave input (i.e. below the cutoff frequency) with a peak-to-peak voltage of 200 mV (blue). (h) Output (red) when using a 100 kHz (i.e. above the cutoff frequency) sine wave input with a peak-to-peak voltage of 200 mV (blue). (i) Voltage (blue) and current (red) supplied by the battery upon switching on the buffer circuit with a 1 kHz sine wave input.

A low-voltage OPAMP (Onsemi NCV2001SN2T1G), which can operate with 0.9 V supply while ensuring low bias current and wide bandwidth - therefore potentially suitable to be operated by a single edible battery - was selected. The component packaging (SOT-23) did not allow a convenient connection with the battery. Thus, an SMD adapter (KeeYees SMD SOT-23 - DIP) was used to interface the component with the battery. To study the compatibility of the edible battery with active circuits, two popular configurations were selected: an inverting amplifier (Fig. 4a) and a buffer-filter cascade (Fig. 4e). In both cases, a single edible battery was used to power up the OPAMP, therefore the OPAMP was operated at a supply voltage lower (~ 0.8 V) than the specifications (> 0.9 V). The inverting amplifier is widely used to amplify a signal from a sensor. The circuit was fed with a sine wave with a 10 mV peak-to-peak voltage, mimicking data from a sensor. The input signal was provided by function generation (Keithley 50MHz 3390) and data was acquired using an oscilloscope (Tektronix 500 MHz MSO4054). Data indicates that the edible battery was successful in supplying power to the OPAMP to perform the amplification, with an average gain of 2.5 V/V and a 180° phase-shift, as expected by design (see Fig. 4b). The experience was replicated with different frequencies of the input (50 Hz, 100 Hz, 130 Hz, see Fig. 4c, 4d), with identical outcomes, demonstrating that the edible battery can support low-power OPAMP-based amplification circuits.

The buffer-filter cascade is also a largely employed configuration, especially as input stage of analog-to-digital (ADC) converters. Driving an ADC with similar circuits ensures at the same time low-pass anti-aliasing filtering, high impedance for the input signal and decoupled low impedance for the ADC. In this test case, the circuit was fed with a sine wave with a 200-mV peak-to-peak voltage while the frequency was swept from 500 Hz to 300 kHz. The same function generator and oscilloscope were used to apply the input and acquire data, respectively. The experiment indicated that the edible battery was successful in powering the OPAMP in this configuration. The circuit exhibited a typical low-pass effect (Fig. 4f), with an estimated cutoff frequency of ~ 59 kHz. As expected, only a buffering effect was observed when using an input frequency lower than the cutoff (see Fig. 4g). Attenuation and shift of the signal were instead observed when the input signal frequency was above the cutoff (see Fig. 4h). In buffer condition with a 1kHz input signal, the lifetime of the battery was in the order of a few minutes. The circuit switch-on was the most power-hungry phase due to a transient current spike (see Fig. 4i). We speculate that the current overshoot might be related to several factors, including (i) bootstrapping operations (typical design choice in energy-efficient designs [49]), (ii) operating the opamp below its optimal supply range, (iii) parasitic effects, and (iv) battery limitations in dynamic performance upon sudden demand of large current upon circuit

switch-on. Further investigation is required to isolate the factors leading to the observed artefact.

D. Discussion

In this study, the edible battery was demonstrated to benefit from good stability over multiple charge-discharge cycles, to be directly compatible with resistive sensors, and to be suitable for powering low-power active components in different configurations (amplification and filtering). However, this study also highlights several limitations that will have to be addressed in future works.

The operating voltage of the battery is low, but this does not necessarily represent a limitation. On the one hand, passive components are directly compatible, the electronics community is spending extensive efforts to produce ultra low-power systems [5, 46 - 48]. On the other, the operating voltage is suitable for implanted or ingestible systems, where higher voltage sources are not practicable due to hydrolysis and compatibility issues. Although the battery can be recharged several times, the limitation is instead on the energy density and therefore its lifetime. From the data herein presented, we can estimate a lifetime of 5.9 h after 100 cycles when supplying a current of 1 μ A with a single charge. Also, the observed reduction of the operating voltage over time is not advisable and can produce a shift in the data (see Fig. 3f) or modulate the performance of the active circuit. As such, at its current state, the battery is suitable only for ultra low-power applications. Improving the performance of the battery is needed to accommodate applications involving, for instance, wireless communications, where hundreds of μ A might be required. Other conceivable solutions also include using multiple batteries (either in series and/or in parallel) and pairing the batteries with energy harvesting devices, so that the battery pack can be repeatedly recharged, effectively prolonging the lifetime of the device. Interfacing the battery with traditional electronics is also not trivial. Traditional electronics can benefit from a high standardization in packaging and interconnections while the battery employs uncommon materials (flexible ethyl cellulose) and topology (stacked electrodes). Unsecured or weak connections can create high contact resistance between the battery and the device, producing a degradation of the performance.

IV. CONCLUSION

Recently, a non-toxic organic battery produced in [19] was selected as one of the best innovations of 2023 by TIME [21]. The battery is entirely produced using food-derived materials and therefore can be used in direct contact with food with no contamination risk. This feature opens novel scenarios for sensors-on-food and sensors-in-package applications.

This work explored the possibility of powering up sensing nodes for agrifood applications using the above-mentioned battery. Despite further work is needed to improve the performance of the battery mainly in terms of energy density and lifetime, this study shows that the edible battery is indeed a viable option to power up simple low-power circuits. Here we demonstrated the use of the battery for basic blocks of any readout circuits, i.e. sensing, amplification, and filtering. We believe this work can motivate the research community to

consider the sustainability of the system as one of the objectives for technological innovation and spark a quest for greener components employable instead of traditional ones in suitable applications.

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